

MASTER THESIS

**Targeted meiotic DNA Double strand break induction using the CRISPR/Cas9 system
analyzed via single pollen genotyping**

Submitted by

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List of abbreviations

°C	degree Celsius
µg	Microgram
µl	Microliter
mM	Micromolar
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BAM	Binary alignment Maps
Bp	base pair
C	Cytosine
Cas	CRISPR-associated
CRISPR	clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats
crRNA	CRISPR RNA
dH₂O	deionized water
DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid
dNTP	deoxy nucleotide triphosphate
DSB	double-strand break
EB	extraction buffer
EDTA	ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
g	Gram
G	Guanine
gRNA	guide RNA
gDNA	genomic DNA
HCl	hydrogen chloride
HDR	homology-directed repair
hr	Hours
H₂SO₄	sulfuric acid
InDels	insertions or deletions
kb	Kilobase
l	Liter
IGV	Integrative Genomics Viewer
IDT	Integrated DNA Technologies
LB	Luria-Bertani
LD	long day
M	Molar
Mb	Megabases
mg	Milligram
min	Minutes
ml	Milliliter
mM	Millimolar
MS	Murashige and Skoog
NaCl	sodium chloride
Neg	negative control
ng	Nanogram
NHEJ	non-homologous end joining

NLS	nuclear localization signal
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
PAM	protospacer adjacent motif
PCR	polymerase chain reaction
PEG	polyethylene glycol
RNA	ribonucleic acid
rpm	revolutions per minute
SDS	sodium dodecyl sulfate
SAM	Sequence Alignment Maps
sgRNA	single guide RNA
SSNs	sequence specific nucleases
T	Thymine
TALEN	transcription activator-like effector nuclease
Taq	<i>Thermus aquaticus</i>
Tm	melting temperature
tracrRNA	trans-activating crRNA
tris	tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane
U	Unit
V	Volt
v/v	volume /volume
w/v	weight/volume
ZFN	zinc-finger nuclease

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Summary

The increasing population demands improved agriculture production in terms of yield and quality to fulfill their needs. Enhanced agriculture production technology can contribute to it by adopting innovative breeding technologies. The pivotal goal of breeders is to generate new crop varieties that outperform their parental lines by combining their traits of interest. These traits of interest are reshuffled in the next progeny via homologous recombination (HR) during meiosis. Meiotic recombination is a specialized process that starts with the induction of DNA double-strand breaks (DSB) during meiosis that are repaired as crossover (CO, resulting in new parental chromosome combinations) or as non-crossover (NCO, restoring the previous situation). An increase or induction of DSB formation during meiosis in specific loci could stimulate meiotic recombination in these loci. Thus, targeted recombination approaches could accelerate breeding processes by inheriting preferred haplotypes.

In this project, the genome-editing tool CRISPR/Cas9 was explored to trigger site-specific meiotic DSB formation *in planta*. Moreover, a novel high-throughput method to detect meiotic HR outcome at defined loci based on single pollen nuclei genotyping as a tool to evaluate meiotic HR frequency at distinct loci including CRISPR/Cas9 targeted loci was explored. Initially various Cas9 target sites were selected *in silico* based on location within polymorphic regions (flanking SNPs or InDels rich regions to track meiotic HR outcome in vicinity of target sites) between *Arabidopsis thaliana* ecotypes Col and Ler. Activity of four of these sites was confirmed *in planta* based on deep amplicon sequencing from transfected protoplasts. Moreover, Col/Ler hybrids and *mtopvib* mutant plants were transformed with constructs consisting of dCas9 (catalytically inactive Cas9) fused to MTOVIB (part of the endogenous DSB induction complex) combined with selected gRNAs in order to stimulate the activity of the endogenous DSB complex at target sites to induce meiotic DSBs. The employed dCas9-MTOVIB functionally complemented *mtopvib* suggesting formation of an active DSB induction containing dCas9-MTOVIB. In addition, from all isolated transgenic lines the genotype was established (i.e. either Col or Ler inbreds or hybrids at target sites) and pollen samples were collected. The outcome of induced DSBs during male meiosis in these plants at target sites was evaluated via novel tool developed during this study, employing NGS amplicon sequencing approach to genotype single pollen nuclei. To enable pollen nuclei genotyping in high-throughput at target sites, a novel approach using targeted NGS amplicon sequencing combined with a tailor-made bioinformatics pipeline to genotype single pollen nuclei (“plant sperm-typing”) was established that can be extended to any locus of choice not only limited to *A. thaliana*.

Resumen

El incremento constante de la población necesita que la producción agrícola mejore en términos de rendimiento y calidad para asegurar la disponibilidad de alimento. Un avance en la tecnología de producción agrícola puede contribuir a ello a través de la adopción de procedimientos de mejora vegetal innovadores. El objetivo fundamental de los mejoradores vegetales es generar nuevas variedades de cultivos que superen a sus líneas parentales al combinar sus características de interés. Estos rasgos de interés se mezclan en la siguiente generación mediante el proceso de recombinación homóloga (HR) que ocurre durante la meiosis. La recombinación meiótica es un proceso especializado que comienza con la inducción de roturas de doble hebra de ADN (DSB) durante la meiosis que se reparan como sobrecruzamientos (CO, generando nuevas combinaciones de cromosomas parentales) o como no sobrecruzamiento (NCO, restaurando la situación anterior). Un aumento del número de DSB durante la meiosis, o la inducción de estas en loci específicos podría estimular la recombinación meiótica en estos loci. Por tanto, la recombinación dirigida podría acelerar los procesos de mejora vegetal permitiendo la transferencia de los haplotipos deseados.

En este proyecto hemos utilizado la herramienta de edición del genoma CRISPR / Cas9 para generar DSB en loci predefinidos *en planta*. Además, hemos evaluado el potencial de un nuevo método para detectar con alto rendimiento el resultado de la HR en los sitios diana. Este método se basa en genotipar un único núcleo de polen para así para evaluar la frecuencia de la HR meiótica en distintos loci, incluidos los loci diana de CRISPR / Cas9. Inicialmente se seleccionaron *in silico* varios sitios diana de Cas9 en función de la ubicación dentro de regiones polimórficas entre los ecotipos Col y Ler de *Arabidopsis thaliana* (SNP flanqueantes o regiones ricas en InDels para rastrear el resultado de la HR meiótica en las proximidades de los sitios diana). La actividad de cuatro de estos sitios se confirmó *en planta* mediante secuenciación de amplicones de protoplastos transfectados. Además, los híbridos Col / Ler y las plantas mutantes de *mtopvib* se transformaron con construcciones que consistían en dCas9 (Cas9 catalíticamente inactivo) fusionado con MTOVIB (parte del complejo proteico de inducción de DSB endógeno) combinado con gRNA seleccionados para estimular la actividad de dicho complejo proteico en los sitios diana para inducir DSB. La construcción dCas9-MTOVIB complementó funcionalmente *mtopvib*, lo que sugiere que dCas9-MTOVIB es capaz de formar DSB. Además, en todas las líneas transgénicas aisladas se estableció el genotipo (es decir, puras o híbridos Col o Ler en los sitios diana) y se recogieron muestras de polen. El resultado de las DSB inducidas durante la meiosis masculina en estas plantas en los sitios diana se evaluó mediante una nueva herramienta desarrollada durante este estudio, que emplea el método de secuenciación de amplicones NGS para genotipar núcleos de polen individuales. Para permitir el genotipado de núcleos de polen con alto rendimiento en los sitios diana, se estableció un enfoque novedoso que utiliza la secuenciación de amplicones NGS combinada con un protocolo bioinformático diseñado para genotipar núcleos de polen individuales ("tipificación de espermatozoides de plantas") que se puede extender a cualquier locus seleccionado y que no está limitado a *A. thaliana*

Sommaire

La population croissante exige une production agricole améliorée en termes de rendement et de qualité pour répondre à leurs besoins. Une technologie de production agricole améliorée peut y contribuer en adoptant des technologies de sélection innovantes. L'objectif central des sélectionneurs est de générer de nouvelles variétés de cultures qui surpassent leurs lignées parentales en combinant leurs caractères d'intérêt. Ces traits d'intérêt sont remaniés dans la descendance suivante via la recombinaison homologe (HR) au cours de la méiose. La recombinaison méiotique est un processus spécialisé qui commence par l'induction de cassures double brin de l'ADN (DSB) pendant la méiose qui sont réparées sous forme de croisement (CO, entraînant de nouvelles combinaisons de chromosomes parentaux) ou de non-croisement (NCO, rétablissant la situation précédente). Une augmentation ou une induction de la formation de DSB pendant la méiose dans des loci spécifiques pourrait stimuler la recombinaison méiotique dans ces loci. Ainsi, des approches de recombinaison ciblées pourraient accélérer les processus de sélection en héritant des haplotypes préférés.

Dans ce projet, l'outil d'édition du génome CRISPR / Cas9 a été exploré pour déclencher la formation de DSB méiotique spécifique au site *dans planta*. De plus, une nouvelle méthode à haut débit pour détecter le résultat de la HR méiotique à des locus définis basée sur le génotypage de noyaux de pollen uniques comme outil pour évaluer la fréquence de la HR méiotique à différents loci, y compris les loci ciblés CRISPR / Cas9, a été explorée. Initialement, divers sites cibles Cas9 ont été sélectionnés *in silico* en fonction de leur emplacement dans des régions polymorphes (régions riches en SNP ou en InDels flanquant pour suivre les résultats de la HR méiotique à proximité des sites cibles) entre les écotypes d'*Arabidopsis thaliana* Col et Ler. L'activité de quatre de ces sites a été confirmée chez *planta* sur la base d'un séquençage d'amplicon profond à partir de protoplastes transfectés. De plus, des hybrides Col / Ler et des plantes mutantes *mtopvib* ont été transformés avec des constructions constituées de dCas9 (Cas9 catalytiquement inactif) fusionné à MTOVIB (partie du complexe d'induction DSB endogène) combiné avec des ARNg sélectionnés afin de stimuler l'activité du complexe DSB endogène à sites cibles pour induire des DSB méiotiques. Le dCas9-MTOVIB employé a complété fonctionnellement le *mtopvib* suggérant la formation d'une induction active de DSB contenant dCas9-MTOVIB. De plus, à partir de toutes les lignées transgéniques isolées, le génotype a été établi (c'est-à-dire soit des consanguines Col ou Ler soit des hybrides sur des sites cibles) et des échantillons de pollen ont été collectés. Le résultat des DSB induits au cours de la méiose mâle chez ces plantes sur des sites cibles a été évalué via un nouvel outil développé au cours de cette étude, en utilisant une approche de séquençage d'amplicon NGS pour des noyaux de pollen uniques de génotype. Pour permettre le génotypage des noyaux polliniques à haut débit sur les sites cibles, une nouvelle approche utilisant le séquençage d'amplicon NGS ciblé combiné à un pipeline bioinformatique sur mesure pour génotyper des noyaux de pollen uniques (plant sperm-typing) a été mise en place et peut être étendue à n'importe quel locus de choix non seulement limité à *A. thaliana*.

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1. Introduction

Agriculture started 12,000 years ago, giving rise to the era of domestication and cultivation of crops. Barley, lentils and peas were among the first cultivated plants. Time passed and man got engaged in improving crops for their utilization as food, feed and for other crucial resources. Initially, trials for crop improvement started with simple mass selection but with time crop production underwent intense transition. Traditional farming techniques were replaced by new ones. Nowadays, modern technologies in agriculture such as mechanization, fertilization, advanced irrigation techniques or high yielding seeds are employed to agriculture to ensure higher food productivity. Despite of hundreds of advancements in agriculture the problem of hunger and malnutrition still persists in the society. This situation is alarming when demographic data is analyzed. According to the US Census Bureau 2019, the current world population is 7.6 billion, which is expected to increase up to 9.7 billion until 2050. Thereby increasing the global crop demand by 100-110 percent compared to 2005¹. According to FAO's 2019 report, around 800 million people worldwide are chronically hungry and two billion are micronutrient deficient. Combating hunger and providing improved nutrition requires innovative technologies for revolutionizing the global food security system. To do so, among various strategies agricultural practices and technologies will be crucial. Producing sufficient food for an ever-growing population is challenging. While the demand for food is constantly increasing, limited resources are depleted (decreased arable land, water for irrigation, climate change etc.). Progress in plant breeding has contributed to considerable yield growth during the last 100 years and it is still contributing² to it by delivering higher yielding crop varieties with improved traits. To feed upcoming generations and to maintain sustainability, there is an urgent need to adopt innovative breeding technologies to keep pace with the ever-growing demand and to boost agricultural productivity.

Need for new breeding technologies: Breeding technologies such as mutation, cross or transgenic breeding are the major crop improvement technologies at present time. However, it takes years to realize desirable allele combinations by cross breeding to increase variability via genetic recombination³. In addition, due to continuous breeding efforts for decades, some parts of the genomes are already fixed within major crops, thus reducing the available genetic variation. This limits the potential for improving many traits. In contrast, mutation breeding potentially aids in expanding genetic variation by introducing random mutation using physical irradiation or chemical mutagens⁴. However, mutagens are more or less random in their effects and they cause various unwanted alterations in the genome hence generating a large number of mutants. Screening of such a large population makes breeding practices rather complicated, tedious and time consuming.

Accelerated breeding: To accelerate breeding, large efforts were made to increase selection efficiency using marker assisted selection (MAS)⁵ and genomic selection⁶. However, these marker-based approaches are limited by their reliance on markers and genetic diversity available in populations^{3,7}. Transgenic breeding generating desired traits through transfer of exogenous genes in elite background varieties can break the bottleneck of reproductive isolation⁷. However, generation and application of genetically modified organism is problematic due to their restricted commercialization, tough regulatory evaluation processes and public interests⁸. These and other shortcomings denoted the need of targeted breeding approaches. Trials and experimentation for targeted approach started long time ago. In 1988, already the first gene targeting experiment in *Nicotiana tabacum* protoplasts was performed⁹ followed by the discovery of the potential of DNA double strand breaks (DSBs) for enhanced gene targeting. Accordingly, the scientific community was striving for the discovery and development of precise tools for targeted genome editing in plants. Zinc finger nucleases (ZFNs)¹⁰ employed in 2005 and transcription activator like effector nucleases (TALENs)¹¹ employed in 2010 added advancements in targeted genome editing approaches in plants. In 2013, CRISPR/Cas9¹² (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats/CRISPR-associated protein 9) dramatically increased the potential for improving traits in breeding programs based on targeted genome editing in plants (for details see section 2.5). Several traits have been modified using CRISPR/Cas9 including yield potential, biotic and abiotic stress response, yield quality etc. This novel genome editing tool also helped breeders to enhance hybrid breeding technology and aided to eliminate unwanted traits and to add the desired ones in elite varieties. It even enables trait modification in crops in a single generation.¹³ Thus, CRISPR/Cas9 holds great promise for improving agricultural practices, and thus contributing to global food security.

Plant breeders are dependent on novel genetic variations generated by crossover (CO), resulting in new parental chromosome combinations during meiosis, to develop new and superior varieties. However, in crop plants this variation is typically limited and a large part of the genetic material remains untouched. CO distribution follows skewed distribution towards sub telomeric chromosome regions in maize¹⁴, tomato¹⁵, wheat¹⁶ and barley¹⁷. In species like Arabidopsis, maize and wheat small regions of 1-2 KB are found to have comparatively high recombination rates¹⁸. In cereal crops such as barley being important for fodder, feed, brewing industry large distortions of meiotic recombination events along chromosomes are found. Therefore, a large amount of genetic variation naturally present in the crops is left unexploited despite high its potential for developing new varieties. In addition, it also restricts gene isolations, creates linkage drag or restricts the introgression of new genetic traits. Therefore, site directed modification of meiotic recombination has great potential for accelerating plant breeding¹⁷ and accordingly there is need to devise new technologies and to implement them in crop breeding programs for the isolation of better and improved varieties.

Need for precise targeted meiotic recombination approaches, since meiotic recombination can not only result in the combination of favorable characters in crops but also produces allelic combinations which are not desired in a particular breeding program. During the production of near homozygotes by making inbred or double haploid lines there is always a chance of CO formation during meiosis in the homologues of inbred within breeding materials, which makes the process complicated, resulting in non-identical homologues i.e. different allelic combinations. Therefore, there is need to employ novel breeding methods harnessing or modifying meiotic recombination outcome in order to generate new allele and chromosome combinations. These novel combinations should be desirably fixed for the later use in generating homozygous breeding materials. Since genetic variation is assured by homologous recombination (HR) during meiosis, when programmed meiotic DSBs are alternatively repaired as CO (resulting in new parental chromosome combinations) or as non-crossover (NCO, restoring the previous situation), targeted meiotic DSB formation employing the CRISPR/Cas9 system holds great promise for manipulating and inducing meiotic recombination events to be implemented in breeding programs.

2. Literature review

Evolution on the planet is driven by genetic variations occurring in the environment. Genetic variations refer to genetic differences in specific populations or individuals being the basis of evolution in nearly almost all organisms. These variations can be the result of changing environments or natural selection over time. Natural selection is responsible for increasing or decreasing the frequency of alleles present in a population, thereby manipulating the genetic setup of an organism. When all genetic variations are combined together, it forms Genetic diversity. This genetic diversity or variations in eukaryotes are caused by various factors including mutation, random mating, random fertilization or crossing over (CO) between homologous chromosomes during meiosis. Except mutations, all other factors are responsible for reshuffling alleles within populations and for giving rise to progeny genetically diverse from either of their parents and to each other. Among all, meiosis is the most salient one, by ensuring that all sexually reproducing organisms produce novel progeny and also produce genetic variation by the process of meiotic homologous recombination (HR).

2.1 Meiosis – key event for sexual reproduction

Meiosis is a specialized form of a cell division critical for sexually reproducing organisms that underpins fertility and genetic variation through HR. The role of meiosis is two-fold: chromosome number reduction and genetic variation. First, chromosome number reduction is essential to assure ploidy maintenance upon fusion of male and female gametes. Second, meiotic homologous recombination is the basis of genetic variation in almost all eukaryotes (having sexual reproduction), including plants and animals. These genetic variants are established in populations forming stable genetic modifications, which are the result of underlying changes in the allelic combinations along the chromosomes.

The process of meiosis consists of a single round of DNA replication followed by two consecutive rounds of chromosome segregation, named meiosis I and meiosis II. Meiosis I is a reductional division, that halves the number of chromosomes in resulting daughter cells. During meiosis a series of specialized events take place (Fig1). Before initiation of meiosis, the cells undergo G1 phase (cell growth phase) before replicating their DNA during a phase called Synthesis phase (S-phase). Finally, the cells undergo G2 phase which prepares them for the following meiotic divisions marking the end of pre-meiotic events. It consists of four different stages called prophase, metaphase, anaphase and telophase (all of them occur twice during meiosis I and meiosis II). Meiosis I starts with a prolonged prophase I subdivided into Leptotene, Zygotene, Pachytene, Diplotene and Diakinesis. The major events during this prolonged prophase I include homologous recombination, chromosome condensation and co-alignment of the chromosomes with their homologous pairs (pairs of same size and similar genes) along their length, that

culminate in a tight pairing of homologous chromosomes during synapsis. During late prophase I, reciprocal genetic exchange between synapsed homologous chromosomes occurs resulting in the formation of CO (Fig1). Thus, meiotic HR during prophase I can result in CO or reciprocal swapping of the genetic materials creating novel allele combinations in form of unique chromosomes^{19,20}. Prophase I is followed by metaphase I, during which recombined (physically connected by meiotic recombination events) homologous chromosomes are aligned at the metaphase I plate. At this stage microtubules emerge forming spindles and attach to the kinetochore at centromeres of the chromosomes. Anaphase I marks separation of the homologous chromosomes towards opposite poles and the disassembly of microtubules. At this point, sister chromatids of separated homologous chromosomes are connected while chromosome number is halved (Fig 1). Finally, during telophase I cytoplasm organization takes place. During the second meiotic division (equational division, no reduction in the chromosome number), sister chromatid separation occurs resulting in the formation of four haploid cells that will give rise to the gametes. Thus, finally four genetically non-identical daughter cells with half of the original amount of genetic materials are formed. Each cell contains a new mixture of genes along chromosomes (due to HR during meiosis I).

Fig1. Schematic overview of meiosis. Meiosis reduces the chromosome number by two consecutive rounds of nuclear divisions (during meiosis I and meiosis II) after one round of DNA replication. Depicted a single diploid parental cell (both homologous chromosomes) undergoing meiosis I and meiosis II resulting in the formation of four haploids daughter cells. Note, four haploid cells are genetically not identical due to the process of homologous recombination.

Genetic variants arising during meiosis are novel and diverse due to genetic blending by recombination and independent homologous chromosome assortment. These events are dependent on the number and position of CO sites (intrachromosomal recombination: based on a CO between similar loci of homologous chromosome) and the number of chromosomes

(intrachromosomal recombination: based on the independent assortment of homologous chromosome). While chromosome number is typically fixed, CO incidence varies between bivalents, chromatids, cells, sexes, individuals and species^{21,22}. Moreover, in plants CO number rarely exceeds three per chromosome and limited formed CO are typically found heterogeneously along chromosomes enriched in “hot spot” regions inhibiting access to traits in “cold” regions. Thus, breeding programs do not exploit a large pool of potential genetic variation naturally available for the development of new varieties due to limited and skewed meiotic recombination events.

2.2 Meiosis assures genetic variation – harnessed during breeding

Plant breeding is responsible for creation of novel varieties which are known for their quality and yield related traits. All these traits are generated by selection of useful variation in the plant system over their life cycle. Intensive plant breeding programs including vast selection cycle are involved to detect and select important variations. These activities are tedious, costly and time consuming. Breeding methods like cross, transgenic or randomly induced mutation breeding can take up to 8-12 years for creating a single variety. However, genome editing mediated breeding, induced via endogenous gene modifications take almost half i.e. 4-5 years for making an elite variety. Almost in all breeding programs the major fraction of time is imparted in the selection and screening of the population with desirable traits. They are achieved by a number of tools such as foreign gene integration, backcrossing, using mutant seeds after physical or chemical treatment or employing molecular marker. Molecular and genetic techniques have accelerated the breeding programs to great extent²³.

For breeders, traditionally breeding progress towards superior varieties relies on selecting favorable traits. Variation and selection in breeding material is assured by meiotic recombination generating (random) novel genetic variations that are harnessed during breeding programs. Naturally reshuffled allelic variation serves as starting material for crop improvement. Therefore, crop improvement can be described as “the reshuffling of the genome to produce new favorable gene combinations in the progeny”²⁴. With an ever-increasing demand for calories by a growing world population in the face of unpredictable biotic and abiotic factors, there is pressing need to improve crop varieties to ensure Food Security in the foreseeable future based on creation of crop varieties with novel allelic combinations, which is one of the prime goals within the plant breeding community.

Meiotic recombination can result in the combination of favorable characters but it also produces allelic combinations which are not desired in particular breeding programs and unpredictability

of such variations leads to time consuming breeding practices^{25,26}. To deal with such variations, there is a need to explore novel and precise tools and techniques for the generation and selection of variation. For instance, during production of near homozygotes by making inbred or double haploid lines there is always a chance of CO formation during meiosis in the homologues of inbreds within breeding materials, which makes the process complicated, resulting in non-identical homologues i.e. different allelic combinations. Therefore, there is pressing need to employ novel breeding methods related to meiotic recombination for generating new allele and chromosome combinations. Also, these combinations should be desirably fixed for the later use in generating homozygous breeding material.

Breeders are mostly interested to modify the natural CO landscape (the number and distribution of CO) e.g. by inducing CO in specific chromosome regions or increasing CO frequency to generate new allelic combinations with superior breeding values²⁷⁻²⁹. Breeding value can be defined as the sum of the average effect of alleles or the value of genes to progeny. It contributes to the additive genetic effect and marks the dominant deviation in the progeny³⁰. The events of recombination and CO formation are major contributors to this deviation (in constant environmental condition). During meiosis new alleles and chromosome combinations are formed through HR^{31,32}, creating genotypes/genetic variants by recombining the preexisting variation in the genotypes. However, in plants meiotic HR events are typically limited in number and their distribution along chromosomes, representing a bottleneck in breeding programs. Thus, novel tools and techniques are needed to alter and manipulate frequency and position of meiotic recombination events, i.e. meiotic recombination landscapes.

2.3 Meiotic HR assures genetic variation

Meiotic HR is responsible for the generation of sequence variation in gametes. It starts with numerous programmed DNA double strand breaks (DSB) mediated by the SPO11/MTOPVIB-complex and associated factors. The repair of these DSB is facilitated by HR leading to the formation of CO (using as repair template the homologous chromosome resulting in new parental chromosome combinations) or non-CO (NCO; using as repair template either the sister chromatid, restoring the previous situation, or using the homologous chromosome resulting in NCO gene conversion (NCO-GC), i.e. non-reciprocal exchange of short DNA stretches between alleles). Tight regulation of meiotic HR assures the formation of at least one CO per chromosome pair obligatory for proper meiotic chromosome segregation. Despite a high number of programmed meiotic DSBs, rarely more than three CO per chromosome are formed per meiosis independent of chromosome/genome size³³⁻³⁵; for instance in barley ~400-500 DSBs result in 18-22 CO, while

around ~200-250 DSBs in *A. thaliana* result in 9-11 CO per meiosis. Thus, different levels of regulation limit the number and distribution of CO throughout the genome reducing genetic variation that can be captured by plant breeding programs. The low frequency and restricted patterning of CO requires breeders to work with large populations over many generations to capture desirable haplotypes and also to get rid of linkage drag³⁶.

Fig2. DSB repair during meiosis. 1. Red and blue colored lines denote a sister chromatid from each homologous chromosome of a homologous chromosome pair. SDSA only produces NCO while after strand invasion HR mediated DSB repair can result in CO formation. After gap filling and ligation, formation of a double holiday junction takes place which is resolved either as CO or NCO. 2. Non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) ligates the broken ends.

2.4 Targeted Meiotic HR to improve and accelerate breeding?

Targeted meiotic DSB formation could be a potential tool to manipulate/induce meiotic recombination events, which can be further implemented in breeding programs. Breeding employing targeted mutagenesis techniques is performed with site-directed nucleases (SDN). Site directed mutagenesis is a precise technique harnessing the cell's imprecise repair mechanism for the repair of site-specific induced DSBs by an SDN. Over the last years various programmable SDNs were employed for the induction of site-specific artificial DSBs, e.g. targeted site-specific induction of DSBs is the basis of genome editing in most eukaryotes. Genome editing technologies enable to perform knockout, chromosomal recombination and site directed

insertion/substitution at specific sites of chromosomal regions or genes. In short, all SDNs are capable of producing DSB at specific loci throughout eukaryotic genomes.

Artificial DSB induction at specific sites can be achieved using genome editing technologies employing SDNs. Three main SDN technologies are primarily used, these are zinc finger nucleases (ZFNs), Transcription activator like effector nucleases (TALENs) and the clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats/CRISPR associated protein 9 (CRISPR/Cas9). Among them^{10,11}, ZFNs are known for its high cost and imprecise DNA sequence recognition^{37,38}. In addition to ZFNs, TALENs derived from *Xanthomonas* bacteria were harnessed as genome editing tools³⁹⁻⁴². However, the complicated tandem repeat feature in the DNA binding domains of TALEN proteins make their design and construction tedious, which account for the limited use of this system. More recently the CRISPR/Cas9 system has emerged as powerful and rather simple genome editing tool in plants and is thus widely used.

2.5 CRISPR/Cas9 as an emerging tool for plant breeders

CRISPR-systems are derived from prokaryotic genomes (bacteria and archaea). In prokaryotes these sequences are known for detecting and destroying infection causing bacteriophages, thereby imparting immunity. The cell employs CRISPR elements to distinguish between genomic and invading DNA⁴³. The conventionally used CRISPR-Cas9 technology is based on the adaptive type II immune system of *Streptococcus pyogenes*, which comprises interaction of three crucial components: the Cas9 protein, the single-guide RNA (sgRNA) and the 20-bp target site situated upstream of the protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) sequence. The sgRNA is a chimeric structure of the *trans*-activating RNA (tracrRNA) and CRISPR RNA (crRNA) expressing the target sequence⁴⁴. The Cas9 protein contains domains homologous to both HNH and RuvC, conferring endonuclease activity and a DNA binding domain, which together with the sgRNA binds to the targeted DNA sequence. Following the detection of the target site, the sgRNA and Cas9 form a complex. The endonuclease domains HNH and RuvC of Cas9, introduces nicks in the complementary as well as non-complementary sequence of DNA respectively which results in a DSB. This DSB occurs mostly a few nucleotides upstream of the PAM site⁴⁵. With the discovery of CRISPR/Cas9 mechanism, researchers started to utilize it for the induction of site directed genome editing or modification of specific regions of host DNA. For genome editing in plants, Cas nucleases derived from the CRISPR/Cas9-system are mostly used for the induction of artificial DSBs⁴⁶. It is a rather simple and cost-efficient approach compared to other SDNs. The guide RNA and Cas protein are typically encoded by a transgene inserted in a plant genome through genetic transformations. A variety of delivery methods such as *A. tumefaciens* mediated

transformation, protoplast transfection, and particle bombardment can be used for the successful integration of CRISPR-Cas9 components into plant genomes for genome editing. CRISPR/Cas9 added practicable advances for trait improvements in crops compared to traditional breeding. CRISPR/Cas9 is also a powerful tool for introducing heritable, trait-related mutations indistinguishable from natural allelic variants⁴⁷.

In addition to Cas9, nuclease-dead Cas9 or dCas9 which is enzymatically inactive is employed widely in research activities. Some of the applications of the dCas9 system includes gene activation and repression, epigenome editing, modulation of chromatin topography, live cell chromatin imaging or DNA free gene modifications⁴⁸. Despite of being unable to cleave DNA, dCas9 can be utilized for efficient targeting of selected loci. The dCas9 system can deploy transcriptional activators at its N and C terminus⁴⁹ enabling the regulation of the expression of endogenous target genes without modifying the genome. Therefore, it can be utilized for genetic screening, protein expression and regulating the expression of target genes based on a variety of transcriptional activators or repressors⁴⁸.

2.6 Artificial induction of meiotic HR for crop improvement

Meiotic DSBs are the source for meiotic HR (Fig2). Meiotic HR and resulting meiotic recombination patterns (recombination landscape) are also governed in concert by genetic, epigenetic and environmental factors⁵⁰. Recombination rates can highly vary between species, populations, individuals or chromosomal regions in an organism⁵¹. Moreover, in plants CO number rarely exceeds three per chromosome and limited formed CO are typically found heterogeneously along chromosomes. Thus, modifying meiotic recombination landscapes holds great promise to improve and accelerate plant breeding programs.

In *S. cerevisiae*, several approaches were successfully tested to induce DSB and CO formation at specific sites in the genome using SPO11 fusions with DNA-binding proteins, such as zinc fingers, TALEN modules and Cas9^{52,53}. In *Solanum pimpinellifolium* targeted somatic HR can be triggered based on Cas9-induced DSBs⁵⁴. In addition, our previous work (Steckenborn et al., unpublished) has shown that in a meiotic DSB-defective plant (i.e. no HR triggered CO formation) induction of artificial DSBs randomly throughout the genome (DNA damaging agents) can rescue meiotic CO formation as well as that expression of a catalytically-inactive dCas9 fused with MTOPVIB (dCas9-MTOPVIB; part of the endogenous meiotic DSB-induction complex) fully restores CO formation in DSB-defective *mtopvib* plants, potentially leading to a variation in recombination rates at specific loci. These approaches are promising for increasing CO frequency in specific genomic regions in plants. Targeted meiotic DSB formation could help as potential

tool to manipulate/induce meiotic recombination events, which can be further implemented in breeding programs for improving the yield and quality traits^{55–58}.

2.7. How to measure meiotic HR in high throughput

Several techniques exist to measure recombination rates¹⁷, such as cytologically by meiotic chromosome spread analysis^{59,60}, genotyping-by-sequencing and molecular markers^{14,61,62} in large segregating F₂ populations or fluorescent transgenic lines. As alternative, microspore (tetrad or pollen nuclei) genotyping or sequencing as well as pollen typing were developed to measure recombination directly in meiotic products^{14,61,62}. Unfortunately, a time-consuming generation of FTLs in crops or sequencing/genotyping of crop microspores is expensive and limited in numbers. In barley single pollen nuclei genotyping consists of isolating individual haploid pollen nuclei from F₁ hybrids by utilizing fluorescence activated cell sorting (FACS) followed by whole-genome amplification (WGA) and subsequent multi-locus KASP-genotyping or single-cell genome sequencing. Similar approaches were also recently employed harnessing linked-read sequencing in plants and non-plant species. These pioneering techniques enable measuring recombination rates from gametes before fertilization without the need for growing large segregation populations^{50,61}. However, all methods either rely on WGA of every single pollen nucleus due to their limited haploid DNA content or are dependent on sophisticated and expensive linked-read sequencing platforms, thus limiting the number of analyzed samples. In sum, measuring meiotic recombination rates in gametes in high-throughput has great potential to be incorporated into breeding programs as it could e.g. enable to measure recombination rates at defined distinct loci in high-throughput without the need of growing large segregating populations.

2.8. Aim of the thesis:

The aim of this thesis is i) to explore the genome editing tool CRISPR/Cas9 to trigger site-specific DSBs during meiosis in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and to ii) establish a novel high-throughput method to detect meiotic HR outcome at defined loci based on single pollen nuclei genotyping as a tool to also evaluate meiotic HR frequency and outcome triggered by CRISPR/Cas9 (Fig 2).

To test whether different dCas9-MTOPVIB constructs can induce meiotic DSBs and thus HR (either CO or NCO-GC), *A. thaliana* Col/Ler hybrids are transformed with dCas9-MTOPVIB constructs targeting various genomic regions. The outcome of these dCas9-MTOPVIB induced DSBs during male meiosis is evaluated using targeted NGS amplicon sequencing to genotype single pollen nuclei (“plant sperm-typing”) in high-throughput.

The work was divided in two work packages (Fig1). Within WP1, constructs composed of dCas9 fused to MTOPVIB together with guide RNAs targeting distinct loci in the *Arabidopsis* genome (*in planta* activity confirmed based protoplasts assays combined with deep amplicon sequencing) were to be used for *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* mediated stable genetic transformation of *A. thaliana* hybrid plants (Col/Ler). Among isolated transgenic lines InDel genotyping was to be employed to select hybrid plants.

Within WP2 the establishment of a novel high-throughput method to detect meiotic HR outcome at defined loci based on single pollen nuclei genotyping via NGS analysis of targeted amplicons was to be done. Developed single pollen nuclei genotyping was to be used to evaluate HR outcome and frequency at loci targeted by dCas9-MTOPVIB variants. Single pollen nuclei genotyping consists of two subparts, an initial isolation of pollen nuclei and their subsequent targeted PCR amplification followed by NGS based target amplicon sequencing and bioinformatic analysis.

Fig3. Schematic plan of thesis work. WP1.1: Employed construct composed of dCas9-MTOPVIB, gRNA and transgene expressing module. WP1.2: *A. tumefaciens*-mediated stable genetic plant transformation. WP1.3: Isolation of transgenic lines and InDel genotyping to select hybrid plants (being heterozygous at targeted loci). WP2.1: Single pollen nuclei isolation and target amplification. WP2.2: NGS based target amplicon sequencing and *in silico* analysis to evaluate meiotic HR outcome at selected loci triggered by dCas9-MTOPVIB.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Plant Work

3.1.1 Plant Material:

A. thaliana Col, Ler, Col/Ler hybrids and *mtopvib-2* (GK-314G09) were grown for 8-12 weeks at short day (8 hours light, 16 hours dark) followed by long day conditions (16 hours light, 8 hours dark) at 21°C.

3.1.2 *A. thaliana* seed collection:

Seeds were harvested through a double mesh of 1 mm diameter.

3.1.3 Seed sterilization:

Seed were sterilized under continuous vortexing in 1 ml of a mixture of 70% EtOH and 0.05% Triton X-100 in dH₂O for 10 min repeated twice. A final washing was performed in 100% EtOH and the seeds were dried on Whatman filter papers under the sterile hood. After vaporization of EtOH, the sterilized seeds were ready for sowing/seed screening.

3.1.4 Stable genetic transformation of *A. thaliana* by floral dip:

On the first day, a single *A. tumefaciens* colony was picked to induce 5 ml LB + antibiotics (Rifampicin 100 µg/ml, Gentamicin 50 µg/ml and plasmid DNA-specific marker antibiotic) as starter culture. The culture was grown for 24 hours at 28°C and 200 rpm. On the second day, presence of plasmid DNA in the culture was confirmed by PCR employing as PCR template an aliquot of the culture diluted 1:50 in dH₂O. Upon PCR confirmation, 1.5 ml of the first day culture was used to inoculate 500 ml LB + antibiotics (Rifampicin 100 µg/ml, Gentamicin 50 µg/ml and plasmid DNA-specific marker antibiotic). This culture was incubated for ≥ 24 hours at 28°C and at 200 rpm. On the fourth day, 2 x 250 ml of culture were centrifuged in 250 ml centrifuges tubes (sterile/autoclaved) for 10 min at 5.000 rpm at 4°C. Meanwhile centrifuging 500 ml of a 5% sucrose solution (25 g sucrose in 500 ml dH₂O) was prepared. After centrifuging, the supernatant was poured off, 100 ml of 5% sucrose solution was added to each tube and the bacterial pellet was resuspended first by pipetting and then by inverting the tube/vortexing. Remaining 5% sucrose solution and 65 µl Silwet-77 was added to each tube (~125 µl Silwet-77 per 500 ml = 0.025%) and mixed. Both tubes/solutions were combined in one suitable vessel (sterile/autoclaved) for *Arabidopsis* plant transformation. Plants, in particular the generative parts (inflorescences), were dipped inside the *Agrobacterium* solution, stirred around for 15 seconds in the solution and incubated horizontally under high humidity (box with wet papers) overnight at RT in darkness. On the fifth day, plants were dried and bagged.

3.1.5 Isolation of transgenic *A. thaliana* plants :

Screening for transgenic plants was done in long day conditions using MS PPT and MS media plates. Seeds were sown after sterilization. Plants with 6-8 leaf structure were transferred to pots.

3.2 Molecular work

3.2.1 Genomic DNA extraction:

After genomic DNA extraction, samples were used immediately or stored at -20°C (LIEBHER comfort refrigerator).

3.2.1.1 Quick genomic DNA extraction method:

About 200-250 mg of fresh leaf material was transferred into 0.5 ml sterile Eppendorf tubes containing 50 µl of extraction buffer (2.5 ml tris-HCL, 500 µl 1 M EDTA, 6.25 ml 2 M KCl) and grinded using sterile Eppendorf tips. After sample incubation at 95°C for 10 min using a PCR machine, samples were stored on ice for 2 minutes, 50 µl of dilution buffer (3% Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) in H₂O) was added, samples were vortexed for 5 sec and centrifuged (SORVALL LEGEND Micro 21R centrifuge from Thermo scientific) at 13.000 rpm for one minute.

3.2.1.2 Genomic DNA extraction using Waite⁶³ protocol:

200-400 mg fresh leaf material collected in a 2 ml Eppendorf tube containing 2 mm glass beads was frozen in liquid nitrogen and powdered at 20 Hz for 30 seconds using a Retsch mill (Retsch MM-400). Tissue powder was dissolved in 800 µl of Extraction buffer (0.2 M Tris-HCL, 0.4 M LiCl, 25 mM EDTA, 1% SDS in ddH₂O) by vortexing, 800 µl of phenol/chloroform/Isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1) was added and samples were vortexed before centrifugation at 13.000 rpm at room temperature. The supernatant was separated in a new 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube, washing the pellet was done with 70% Ethanol (350 µl EtOH), the liquid was poured and the pellet was air-dried. 100 µl of dH₂O was added and DNA was resuspended by shaking at room temperature for 30 min.

3.2.1.3 DNA Extraction from protoplasts :

200 µl of protoplast samples were collected in 0.5 ml sterile Eppendorf tubes containing 15 µl of extraction buffer (2.5 ml tris-HCL, 500 µl 1 M EDTA, 6.25 ml 2 M KCl) and samples were vortexed. After incubation at 95°C for 10 min using a PCR machine (PEQStar from PEQLab), samples were cooled on ice for 2 min. 15 µl of dilution buffer (3% BSA in dH₂O) were added, mixed by vortexing (5 seconds) and samples were centrifuged at 13.000 rpm for one minute.

3.2.2 Polymerase chain reaction (PCR):

Two types of PCR were conducted in a 10 µl reaction volume, containing 0.5 µl of genomic DNA of *A. thaliana* and 0.5 µl of 10 µM forward and reverse primers each. Amplification of DNA was done using GoTaq DNA Polymerase from Promega or Phusion DNA polymerase from NEB using provided standard PCR reaction buffers.

Table1. Composition of PCR mixture using GoTaq or Phusion DNA polymerase.

Composition of PCR with GoTaq DNA Polymerase (10 µL volume)		Composition of PCR with Phusion DNA Polymerase (10 µl volume)	
GoTaq® Green Master Mix 5X	2 µl	Phusion DNA polymerase (1U/µl)	0.1 µl
Forward primer (10 µM)	0.5 µl	Forward primer (10 µM)	0.5 µl
Reverse primer (10 µM)	0.5 µl	Reverse primer (10 µM)	0.5 µl
GoTaq DNA Polymerase (5U/µl)	0.1 µl	5X Phusion Buffer	2 µl
dNTP mix (10 mM)	0.2 µl	dNTP mix (10 mM)	0.2 µl
DNA (~200 ng/µl)	0.5 µl	DNA (~200 ng/µl)	0.5 µl
ddH ₂ O	6.2 µl	ddH ₂ O	6.2 µl

3.2.3 Agarose gel electrophoresis:

To separate DNA according size after enzymatic digest or PCR, agarose gel electrophoresis was performed using Biozyme LE Agarose and 1% of TAE (Tris acetate EDTA) or 0.5% of TBE (Tris Borate EDTA) buffers. DNA was stained using 5 µl of HD green plus DNA stain from INTAS. Visualization of agarose gel was done in a gel documentation system from Cell Biosciences

3.2.4 Preparation of bacterial growth media:

Solid growth media was prepared using agar 15 g/1000 ml and liquid media using LB (10 g tryptone, 5 g yeast extract, 10 g NaCl) and agar (3 g agar in 200 ml of LB). Antibiotics were added to the media according experimental requirements. For List of antibiotics and concentrations used, see appendix.

3.2.5 Transformation of competent *Escherichia coli* cells by heat-shock:

5 µl of plasmid DNA was mixed with 50 µl of NEB5 alpha chemically competent cells and samples were incubated for 30 min on ice. A heat shock was performed by incubating cells at

42°C degrees for 30 sec using a water bath. After an incubation on ice for 5 min, 1 ml of SOC media (0.5% Yeast Extract, 2% Tryptone, 10 mM NaCl, 2.5 mM KCl, 10 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM MgSO₄, 20 mM Glucose) was added and samples were incubated at 37°C degrees for 1 hour shaking. Bacterial solutions were plated on LB media containing selective antibiotics followed by an overnight incubation at 37°C.

3.2.6 Bacterial plasmid DNA extraction:

Individual colonies were picked from plates using sterile Eppendorf tips and transferred to falcon tubes (Cell Star tubes) containing liquid LB media with corresponding selective antibiotics. Bacterial cultures were incubated at 37°C overnight at 200 rpm (Heraeus holding GmbH).

3.2.7 Plasmid DNA isolation:

Plasmid DNA was isolated using Gene JET plasmid miniprep kit from Thermo Fisher Scientific according to manufacturer's instructions or chloroform extraction method. Purified plasmid DNA was eluted in 50 µl of water.

To isolate pDNA via the chloroform extraction method, the bacterial solution was centrifuged for 2 min at 6.800 g, LB media was removed and resuspension buffer (250 µl) was added to dissolve the pellet, lysis solution (250 µl) and neutralization solution was added; mixing was done by inversion. 100% CHCl₃ was added followed by centrifugation for 5 min at 8.000 rpm. 500 µl of the upper layer was collected and transferred to a new Eppendorf tube. DNA was precipitated in 100% EtOH followed by centrifugation for 10 min at 13.000 rpm. The supernatant was removed and the DNA-containing pellet was washed with 70% EtOH and centrifuged for 5 min at 8.000 rpm. After removing the supernatant, the pellet was air-dried, followed by addition of 50 µl of H₂O to resuspend the DNA.

3.2.8 Restriction digestion:

Plasmid DNA enzymatic restriction digest was performed at 37°C overnight. In case of high-fidelity restriction enzymes, digestion time was 3 hours followed by gel electrophoresis. Cut smart buffer from New England BioLabs was used during digestion. *Sbf1*, *Asc1*, *Xho1*, *Bam1*, *Taq1*, *Aat1*, *Aar1*, *ESP-31*, *Nco 1*, *Dpn* were used for enzymatic digests.

Table2. Composition of restriction digestion.

Standard composition of enzymatic restriction enzyme digest reaction	
DNA (~200 ng/µl)	1 µl

Restriction buffer (5X)	2 μ l
Restriction enzyme A (1U/ μ l)	0.25 μ l
Restriction enzyme B (1U/ μ l)	0.25 μ l
ddH ₂ O	6.5 μ l

3.2.9 Molecular cloning:

Two types of molecular cloning approaches were employed.

3.2.9.1 Gibson assembly cloning:

One plasmid from each module (A: dCas9/MTOPVIB/B000/pHTR5, B: dCas9/MTOPVIB/B2303(14a+at5g)/pHTR5, C: dCas9/MTOPVIB/B2303(at2g+RD1)/pHTR5) was selected together with a transformation backbone vector. The cas9 was inserted in A0103⁶⁴ vector, the gRNAs were cloned in the B2515 vector under control of U6 promoter and GFP expression cassette was inserted in C3003 vector, which was altogether combined in pT100 vector system. After selecting module and backbone, a golden gate reaction was set up with 75 ng of transformation vector, 150 ng of module A plasmid, 150 ng of module B plasmid, 150 ng of module C plasmid, 0.4 μ l *Aar1* oligonucleotide with 0.5 μ l *Aar1* enzyme, 1 μ l T4 DNA ligase with 2 μ l of 10X T4 DNA ligase buffer and dH₂O up to 20 μ l. Finally, the reaction was placed in a PCR machine with the following conditions: (37°C/5min +16°C/10min) + 37°C/15min + 80°C/5min + 4°C hold.

3.2.9.2 pJET cloning:

Blunt end cloning was performed using Thermo Fisher Scientific Clone JET PCR cloning kit. The ligation reaction was set up with 10 μ l 2X reaction buffer, 1 μ l PCR product (blunt end DNA fragment), 1 μ l pJET cloning vector, 7 μ l of nuclease free water and 1 μ l of T4 DNA ligase. Ligation mixture was vortexed for some seconds, briefly centrifuged and incubated for 5 min on ice. The 2.5 μ l of ligation mixture and 25 μ l of chemically competent *E. coli* cells were mixed together followed by 45 sec heat shock in water bath followed by incubation of ice for 5 min. The ligation mixture was ready to use after incubation.

3.2.10 DNA Ligation reaction:

DNA from enzymatic reactions was first 5'-dephosphorylated using Shrimp Alkaline phosphatase (SAP) for 1 hour at 37°C and purified using Monarch Kit (see 3.2.12). Gel electrophoresis was performed to estimate DNA amounts and control their quality. A ligation reaction was prepared as follows: 1-unit T4 DNA ligase, 1x T4 DNA ligase buffer, 50 ng of destination vector and 3 times molar concentration of insert compared to the vector. All components were mixed in a final

volume of 20 μ l. The ligation mixture was incubated at 16°C for 1 hr and 10 min at 70°C. 5 μ l of the ligation reaction was used for bacterial transformation.

3.2.11 Agrobacterium tumefaciens transformation:

Electro competent *A. tumefaciens* GV3101 cells were combined with approximately 20 ng of plasmid DNA (10x diluted plasmid DNA samples). Electroporation tubes were used to provide electric shock of one pulse using BioRad Micro pulsator. 1 ml of SOC media was added to the samples and left for 2 hours at 28°C shaking. Bacterial solutions were plated on LB media containing selective antibiotics by incubation for 48 hours at 28°C. For List of antibiotics and concentrations used, see appendix.

3.2.12 DNA cleanup from enzymatic reactions or to concentrate DNA samples:

The Monarch PCR and DNA Cleanup Kit was used according manufacturer's instructions. Purified or concentrated DNA samples were eluted in dH₂O.

3.2.13 Protoplast isolation:

Protoplasts were isolated from mesophyll tissues of *A. thaliana*. From young leaves, 4-5 cm in dimension, the lower surface was peeled off by sticking the forward face of leaf on a paper tape. After peeling, leaves were incubated in an enzyme mix (1.5% cellulose, 0.4% macerozyme, 0.4 M mannitol, 20 mM KCl, 20 mM MES, in dH₂O, pH 5.7) under continuous shaking for 2-3 hours.

3.2.14 Protoplast transformation:

Isolated protoplast cultures were accumulated in big falcon tubes and subjected to gentle centrifugation at 1.000 rpm for 4 min. Twice the supernatant was removed after centrifugation at 1.000 rpm and replaced with W5 solution (154 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 125 mM CaCl₂, 2 mM MES, 1 N KOH). The samples were incubated for 30 min on ice and centrifuged at 1.000 rpm for 4 min. After centrifugation 180 μ l of MMG solution (0.4 M mannitol, 4 mM MES, 15 mM MgCl₂) was added per transformation. 20 μ l of plasmid was added to each tube of 180 μ l protoplast and mixed. 1 volume of PEG solution was added to each tube and the samples were incubated for 10 min at room temperature. To stop the reaction, 1.4 ml of W5 solution was added, samples were incubated for 5 min and centrifuged at 1.000 rpm for 1 min. The supernatant was removed and 2 ml of fresh W5 solution was added. Finally, samples were incubated for 24 to 48 hours at 21°C in 16 well plates.

3.2.15 Estimation of transgene expression levels:

Inflorescences of transgenic plants were dissected on a wet filter paper under a binocular microscope. 3-4 dissected flower buds were squashed onto a slide in Vectashield solution (DAPI

in antifade solution) under a cover slip. Expression of eYFP-NLS was evaluated under Fluorescence microscope (Nikon, X-Cite 120 LED Boost).

3.2.16 Primers

Following set of primers were used for different PCR amplification events:

Table3. For amplification of target sites:

At2gChr3FWR	TGACTGTAAAGCAAGAGAGAG
At2gChr3REV	TACCTTGCAGGTGAGGCC
At2gChr5FWR	GAGATTCAGTGAATTCAGAAGGC
At2gChr5REV	GGAGAGATTAGAGAATCGTGG
Ren1FWR	CTACGGAATGTTACGCGGACG
Ren1REV	CTTTGCATAAAAATGAGAAGCACATC
PCR14aFWR	CCGAAAGAATAATAATTCTAAAC
PCR14aREV	TCCTATGGCAGGCCAAACTCTG
pcrAt5gFWR4	CACTTCTTGACTGCTCATGGG
pcrAt5gREV4	TTCCAGTGCAAACTAACATCACTC
PCR-BIG-AT2Gc5_forward_4	GCTGAAACCGCCATAGAAC
PCR-BIG-AT2Gc5_reverse_4	GCTAATGAGCCCTCCTAAACAC
PCR-BIG-AT2Gc3-forward1	GACAACAACCATTTCAGCTTAAG
PCR-BIG-AT2Gc3-reverse1	TAAGCCCAATAGGCCCAAAC
PCR-BIG-14A_forward	TGGAGAAAAAAAAGGAACCCAG
PCR-BIG-14A_reverse	GTCGAAACAGAGATCGAGAATC
PCR-BIG-Reena1-forward2	AGTTTACAATCTCCAGCAACTC
PCR-BIG-Reena1-reverse2	GTAAAGAAACCCTCACCTTTTCC

Table4. For pJET cloning:

pJET Fwd	CRACTCACTATAGGGAGAGCGGC
pJET Rev	AAGAACATCGATTTTCCATGGCAG

Table5. Primers for cloning (Cloning gRNAs with Esp3I overhang for cloning):

14a1FWR	GATT GAGGCCGTAGACACGCGTAT
14a1REV	AAAC CATACGCGTGTCTACGGCCTC
At5g46490FWR	GATT GTATCTGCGGGGTAGGAATG
At5g46490REV	AAAC CATTCTACCCCGCAGATAC
At2g46510FWR	GATT GAGAGGGAGAGAGAGAGAGA
At2g46510REV	AAAC TCTCTCTCTCTCTCCCTCTC
Reena1FWR	GATT GAGAAGTAGTGAGTCTGTCT
Reena1REV	AAAC AGACAGACTCACTACTTCTC
Reena2FWR	GATT GAGGTAAGTACTTAAATCA
Reena2REV	AAAC TGATTAAGTCAAGTTACCTC
Reena3FWR	GATT GTTTACATAACGATTTGTAT
Reena3REV	AAAC CATACAAATCGTTATGTAAC

Table6. For C3003 cloning:

pHTR5modC3003fwr	GGCGTAATATGGCGCGCCAGATCCGA TATAACAAAATTTG
YFPmodC3003rev	ACTCGAACCTCGAGTCACTTGTACAG CTCGTC

Table7. For sequencing the construct and Agrobacterium PCR:

CAS9_seq_5p_revA	ACTTTAGCCATCTCGTTAGAGAAG
CAS9_seq_3p_fwr	TCGATACAACCATCGATAGGAAG
L4440_prom_seq_fwr	GCAGCGAGTCAGTGAGCGAG
BstXI_ter_seq_rev	CAGGGTTATTGTCTCATTAGCGG
pHTR5_seq_fwr	TTCTGAGGTACGATTCTTCGATCC

Table8. For mutant genotyping:

AtMTOPVIBlongGenotypingFWR4	CGCAAACCCTTTGCTAATCCC
AtMTOPVIBlongGenotypingREV1	CAACCGTTCAAGATTGGAGGC
GABI_LB2(7)	CCCATTTGGACGTGAATGTAGACAC

3.2.17 Antibiotics

Table9. Antibiotics and concentrations used.

Name of antibiotics	Composition (mg/l)
Kanamycin	50
Gentamycin	25
Ampicillin	50
Kanamycin	50
Rifampicillin	50
Spectinomycin	50
Sulfadiazine	50
Glufosinate Ammonium (PPT)	50

3.3 Single pollen typing

Single pollen genotyping consists of the following consecutive steps:

3.3.1 Flower collection:

For each extraction, 30-35 flowers of Col, Ler or Col/Ler hybrid plants were collected in a single 2 mL Eppendorf tube.

3.3.2 Pollen extraction:

Pollen was isolated either in water or acetone from flowers collected (3.21.1). Around 30-35 flowers were collected in 2 ml Eppendorf tubes containing either 400 µl of water or acetone and vortexed, followed by filtration through a Partec CellTrics filters (50 µm mesh) and washed with 400 µl of water or acetone. The filtrate was centrifuged for 5 min at 13.000 rpm to pellet pollen nuclei (the supernatant was removed and the remnant was dried before further use).

3.3.3 Pollen nuclei isolation:

Dried pollen samples were dissolved in Galbraith buffer (100 µl) for lysis of nuclei and then grinded in a Retsch mill at 30 Hz for 20 seconds (steel balls were used to improve pollen grain disruption). The volume of the solution was adjusted to a total volume of 1 ml with 900 µl of Galbraith buffer and then filtered through nylon net filters (Partec Celltrics filters). The nuclei ready for Fluorescence-activated cell sorting FACS were stained with 50 µg/ml of Propidium Iodide (PI) from Invitrogen.

3.3.4 Flow sorting:

Flow sorting of haploid pollen nuclei was done with a BD Influx cell sorter using software BD FACS software 1.2.0.142 in 96 well plates (Tear-a-way 96/8 PCR plate) to accommodate a large number of samples at a time. 0.5X PBS buffer was used for the sorting process. The number of nuclei sorted was variable in each experiment ranging from 3 to 1.000 nuclei at a time. Between five and 20 replicates were done for each sorting.

3.3.5 Nuclei treatment:

To increase nuclei accessibility for PCR, the following nuclei treatments were tested. The PCR machine and sonicator were from PEQStar and TRANSONIC DIGITAL from Schütt Labortechnik, respectively.

3.3.6 Proteinase K treatment:

5 µL of proteinase K (1µg/µl concentration) was used in a PCR reaction mixture of 10 µl (containing NEB Phusion DNA polymerase 0.2 units/µl, 1 µl of 5X NEB Phusion Buffer, 0.2 µl of 10 mM dNTP mix, 0.5µl of 10 µM Forward primer, 0.5µl of 10 µM Reverse primer, 1.7 µl H₂O). The PCR mix was added to the reaction after inactivating proteinase K at 35°C/20min+65°C/20min+90°C/10min.

3.3.7 Sonication:

A water bath sonicator was used for 10 seconds (repeated 3 times) for sonication of the nuclei. After sonication the samples were used as template for PCR (PCR reaction mixture similar to 3.21.5.1).

3.3.8 Proteinase K treatment + Sonication

The time for proteinase K digestion was increased by 15 min and heat inactivation of proteinase K was done followed by sonication with incubation temperature of 35°C/25min+65°C/45min+90°C/15min.

3.3.9 Taq1 restriction enzyme treatment and sonication

A premix containing 3.9 µl of dH₂O + 1 µl of 5X NEB Phusion buffer + 0.1 µl *Taq1* restriction enzyme was used to perform nuclei treatment. Restriction digestion was performed at 65°C for 1 hour prior to sonication and PCR. The samples were subjected to sonication followed by PCR reaction.

3.3.10 BamH1/Xho1 restriction enzyme treatment and sonication

A premix containing 3.9 µl of dH₂O, 1 µl of 5X NEB Phusion buffer, 0.25 µl of *BamH1* and 0.25 µl of *Xho1* was used. Enzymatic digestion was performed at 37°C/1hr and 65°C/15 min prior to sonication and PCR.

3.3.11 Xho1 restriction enzyme treatment and sonication

A premix containing 3.9 µl of dH₂O, 1 µl of 5X NEB Phusion buffer and 0.25 µl of *XhoI* was used. Enzymatic digest was performed at 37°C/1hr and 65°C/15 min prior to sonication and PCR.

3.3.12 PCR reaction composition:

A 5 µl PCR reaction for pollen typing consists of 0.1 µl of Phusion polymerase (0.2units/µl), 1 µl of 5X Phusion buffer, 0.2 µl of 10 mM dNTP mix, Primer 1- 10µm, Primer 2 -10µm, dH₂O- 2.7 µl.

3.3.13 Gel electrophoresis:

Gel electrophoresis (80-100 volts for 50 min) was performed as mentioned in section 3.3 using a 1.7-2.5% 0.5X TBE gel.

3.3.14 DNA extraction from agarose gels:

Gel excision and purification was done using QIAquick Gel extraction kit from QIAGEN according manufacturer's instructions. Purified DNA samples were eluted in water.

3.3.15 Next generation sequencing (NGS analysis) of PCR products :

Purified gel excised PCR amplicons were sent for NGS analysis to the company Genewiz.

3.4 Bioinformatics work

The following set of tools was used for the creation of the bioinformatics pipeline:

3.4.1 Samtools:

Samtool⁶⁵ was used for indexing NGS data and to create alignment maps.

3.4.2 Bowtie 2:

The alignment of the sequence data was done using Bowtie 2.

3.4.3 SNPsplite:

Allele specific alignments were done using SNPsplite. BAM files were used to determine the reads that cover specific SNP positions. The specific library was created with alignment to the reference genome masking all SNP positions with the base 'N'.

3.4.4 Integrative Genome viewer (IGV):

IGV⁶⁶ was used to visualize the alignment maps and for the analysis of sequence data.

3.4.5 Web-based tools:

For InDel genotyping, Col-0 MPI and Ler-0 ecotype sequences available via the Arabidopsis 1001 genomes (<http://signal.salk.edu/atg1001/3.0/gebrowser.php>) were used as reference genomes for primer design.

3.4.6 APE

It was used for basic alignments while designing primers and for performing *in silico* restriction enzyme digests.

3.4.7 Promega

The biomath calculations regarding T_m values and DNA conversions were done using the biomath tool from Promega (<https://www.promega.de/resources/tools/biomath/>).

3.4.8 IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies)

An OligoAnalyzing tool (<https://eu.idtdna.com/calc/analyzer>) provided by IDT was used to analyze primer parameters such as GC content, length, folding and dimerization (Self dimer, hairpin, Heterodimer etc.).

3.4.9 TAIRBLAST 2.9.0+

Specificity of selected primers was controlled by employing the TAIR BLAST tool (<https://www.arabidopsis.org/Blast/index.jsp>).

3.4.10 Serial cloner

Along with ape serial cloner was used to analyze and manipulate sequences such as making the restriction maps, numerically selecting fragments, finding restriction sites, ORF or any nucleotide or peptide sequence, it also calculates T_m of selected fragments, GC content or dynamically determine the translation of selection into peptide and also used calculate molecular weight using a compact interface.

4. Results

4.1 Selection of genomic sites for targeted meiotic DSB induction

In order to induce site-specific (targeted) meiotic DSBs harnessing the endogenous DSB induction complex via the CRISPR/Cas9 system, target sites for Cas9 (i.e. gRNAs) in the *A. thaliana* genome were selected *in silico* and activity of corresponding gRNAs was tested *in planta*.

4.1.1 Selection of genomic sites for targeted meiotic DSB induction: gRNA candidates

Using the *Arabidopsis* 1001 genome assembly, six gRNAs were selected *in silico*. gRNA candidates were selected based on location within polymorphic regions (flanking SNPs or InDels rich region was selected to track meiotic HR in vicinity of gRNA loci) of various degrees between ecotypes Col-0 and Ler-0 and competence for meiotic HR (Table 11).

Table 10. List of selected gRNAs: Name, sequence, chromosomal location and presence/absence in Col and Ler ecotype indicated.

Name	Sequence (without PAM)	Chromosome	Position	Col	Ler
14a1C	GAGCCCGTAGACACCGTAT	4	16696113	yes	yes
At5g46490	GTATCTGCGGGTAGGAATG	5	18852115	yes	no
At2g46510	GAGAGGGAGAGAGAGAGA	3	22044122	yes	no
		5	26728767	yes	no
RD1	GAGAAGTAGTGAGTCTGTCT	1	11293757	yes	yes
RD2	GAGGTAACCTTGACTTAATCA	1	11293810	yes	yes
		5	18850695	yes	yes
RD3	GTTTACATAACGATTTGTAT	1	11294380	yes	no

Genomic regions enriched for Spo11 oligonucleotides (indicative for meiotic DSBs) were chosen to increase the probability of HR induction⁶⁷. In addition, REC8 depleted regions (REC8 abundance negatively correlates with DSB induction) were selected⁶⁸. Target sequences were either present in only one ecotype (Col or Ler), i.e. ecotype-specific, or in both ecotypes. Selected target sequences were located across all *Arabidopsis* chromosomes, except chromosome 2. Four of the selected gRNAs (14a1C, At5g46490, RD1, RD3) were targeting at single distinct loci while the gRNAs At2g46510 and RD2 were targeting two independent loci on two different chromosomes simultaneously.

4.1.2 Activity of selected gRNAs in planta

A transient expression system based on *Arabidopsis* protoplasts combined with NGS-based analysis of amplicons from target sites was employed to evaluate the efficiency of selected

gRNAs to induce artificial site-specific DSBs at selected sites *in planta*. To check the activity of selected gRNAs (designed by Stefan Steckenborn; Table 11), protoplasts were transiently transfected with expression constructs composed of an active Cas9 (in vector A0103⁶⁴), each selected candidate gRNA (RD1, RD2, At5g46490, At2g46510, 14a1C or RD3; Table 1) cloned in vector B2515 under control of the U6 promoter (pU6) and a GFP expression cassette (in vector C3003) all combined together in vector pT100.

Fig4. Depiction of SNPs near PAM and gRNA (At5g46490). The upper nucleotide represents substitution in Col and lower one in Ler. Flanking SNPs are used to identify recombination events within targeted locus.

Based on co-expression of GFP together with Cas9 (encoded from the same plasmid DNA) in transfected protoplasts, identification and quantification of positive protoplast transformants were done via fluorescence microscopic analysis (Fig5). Except for RD2, all other samples were successfully transfected resulting in transfection efficiencies between 20 and 50%, i.e. percentage of GFP-positive protoplasts after transfection, and were used for further analysis.

Fig 5. Microscopic view of transformed protoplasts. Untransformed and transformed protoplasts are GFP-negative or positive. 1. gRNA free Cas9 construct with GFP was used for transformation as positive control based on GFP expression *in planta*. The pictures 2, 3, 4 and 5 represent protoplasts transformed with gRNA 14a1C, At5g4649, At2g46510 or RD1, respectively. The last picture (6) represents the negative control of protoplasts transformed with a construct without gRNA and GFP, hence no GFP fluorescence was observed.

To decipher whether expression of Cas9 together with selected gRNAs results in editing at target sites in transfected protoplasts, initially their genomic DNA was extracted and used for PCR amplification of target loci. These amplicons were sent for paired end NGS (Genewiz). Sequencing of the PCR products revealed mutations at the predicted Cas9 target sites (Fig5) including deletions, insertions, or deletion-accompanied insertions.

Fig6. Editing frequency at targeted gRNA loci. Insertion (green) and deletion (blue), in NGS reads from transfected protoplasts. a.14A1C, b. At5g46490, c. At2g46510-CH5, d. At2g46510-CH3, e.RD1, f.RD3

Signs of editing in the gRNA targets sites was found in all samples despite substantial variation between gRNAs and target sites. Editing frequencies found were between 2.4% and up to 60% after correcting for the variation in protoplast transfection rate per sample (Table12). The editing frequency was comparatively high for At2g46510 with 60% in its target site on chromosome 3 and around 30% in its target locus on chromosome 5, while for RD3 gRNA it was comparatively low with only 2.4%. Thus, it was decided not to continue with RD3 gRNA. The results provide evidence that selected gRNAs in conjunction with Cas9 can precisely generate DSBs at specific sites in the Arabidopsis genome, leading to targeted mutations generated by error-prone NHEJ DNA-repair machinery. Thus, for further analysis the gRNAs with comparatively high editing efficiencies were selected (14a1C, At5g46490, At2g46510, RD1) for generating the final constructs for *Arabidopsis* transformation.

Table112. Illumina paired end sequencing results showing editing frequencies (%) in transfected protoplasts at target sites.

gRNA	Percentage of protoplasts transfected	Editing frequency (%) in transfected protoplasts
14a1C	34	53
At5g46490	50	6
At2g46510 (Ch.3)	20	60
At2g46510 (Ch.5)	20	30
RD1	25	2.4

4.2 Single pollen nuclei genotyping via targeted amplicon NGS analysis

In order to genotype single haploid pollen nuclei in high-throughput at limited cost, a novel single pollen nucleus genotyping approach based on targeted amplicon NGS analysis was established. To do so, thousands of intact pollen nuclei were extracted from *Arabidopsis* Col, Ler, Col/Ler F₁ hybrids. Individual haploid pollen nuclei were isolated via flow cytometry, respective targeted locus was amplified using PCR and NGS-based high-throughput amplicon sequencing data was analyzed via an established tailor-made bioinformatic pipeline.

4.2.1 Pollen nuclei extraction

Pollen nuclei extraction was done via FACS. Flow sorting of single pollen nuclei was done in 96-well PCR plates using Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) as isolation buffer. A flow cytometric gateway for haploid pollen nuclei isolation was employed based on the size of pollen.

Fig7. Flow cytometric overview of haploid pollen nuclei. (A) Flow cytometric diagram of *Arabidopsis* haploid pollen nuclei (1C) in comparison to (B) *Arabidopsis* leaf nuclei (2C or higher due to nuclei in leaves undergoing endoreduplication).

Fig8. Schematic overview of FACS based nuclei sorting. Fluorescence-activated cell sorting is a specialized cytometry approach involving specific light scattering and fluorescence of cells. The fluorescence comes from the cell itself or cells stained with fluorescent molecules, dyes or by labeled antibodies. The sample containing the cells (here pollen nuclei) is suspended in the fluid and kept for sorting. The advantage of this technology is a simultaneous detection of several characteristics of a single cell, enabling to define particular cell types in a heterogeneous population, to assess their frequency and to describe parameter expression. It can be applied to a variety of organisms and cell types including plants. The ability to acquire thousands of events per second quickly generates statistically significant data sets.

Haploid pollen nuclei were extracted from pollen of Col, Ler and Col/Ler hybrid plants using water or acetone as solvent (Fig10). The pollen was either used directly after extraction i.e. fresh or it was stored at -80°C for later use. To evaluate the impact of different storage/extraction procedures, the quantity and quality of single pollen nuclei during flow-cytometry was evaluated. It was found that for fresh pollen samples, water extraction performed better than acetone, while for stored pollen samples acetone extraction performed better than water during flow-sorting (Fig9). The number of events (flow-sorted haploid pollen nuclei) in acetone samples increased by storing at -80°C , while it decreased in case of water stored samples (Fig10). Grinding of extracted pollen suspended in Galbreath buffer at 30 Hz for 30 seconds with steel balls was found the most reliable method for pollen nuclei isolation.

Fig9. Water and acetone-based freshly isolated pollen: samples before (left) and after (right) filtration. Note: Acetone samples are greenish due to higher solubility of acetone than water. Acetone dissolves both polar and non-polar substances.

Fig10. Comparison of extracted pollen nuclei in acetone or water with different storage conditions. A higher number of haploid pollen nuclei was isolated from freshly extracted pollen nuclei (A) in water compared to (B) acetone. (C) Pollen nuclei isolates from stored water samples: no nuclei could be isolated. (D) Acetone stored pollen nuclei: a high number of haploid pollen nuclei can be isolated. Red encircled are the flow-cytometric fraction of haploid pollen nuclei within every sample.

Together, fresh water samples work sufficiently but stored acetone nuclei isolates are the best among tested samples for flow sorting due to their abundant number of isolates. In addition, storage capacity of pollen nuclei at -80°C in acetone offers the advantage of storing pollen samples for further/ later experiments. Therefore, it was decided to continue the work preferably with acetone stored pollen nuclei.

4.2.2 PCR amplification of flow-cytometrically isolated haploid pollen nuclei

It was asked whether pollen nuclei can be used as template for a subsequent PCR targeting the gRNA loci (Table 11). First, isolated nuclei should be accessible for PCR-based pollen genotyping. To improve PCR accessibility, various approaches were tested aiming to destroy the intact nuclei structure. Initially, pollen nuclei were treated with proteinase K. PCR analysis however indicated that Proteinase K is interfering in the PCR reaction, despite prior heat inactivation of Proteinase K. Thus, Proteinase K trials were stopped (Fig 11).

Fig 11. Effect of Proteinase K on pollen nuclei PCR. None of the pollen nuclei samples after Proteinase K treatment showed PCR amplification. When using as PCR template genomic DNA without Proteinase K amplification was observed, while not after Proteinase K treatment.

Next it was decided to use restriction enzymes in order to destroy intact pollen nuclei prior PCR. Using a *TaqI* nuclei pre-treatment consistent PCR amplification from nuclei samples was found (Fig 12). In order to identify the range of nuclei that can be employed in a single PCR reaction (5 μ l total PCR reaction volume), a number of 3, 10, 30, 100, 200, 300, 500 or 1.000 flow-sorted haploid pollen nuclei per reaction was tested in triplicate (Fig 12). Moreover, the sensitivity of pollen typing, i.e. if PCR amplification was achieved from nuclei numbers low as 3, was further checked through *TaqI*. The nuclei range 200-300 showed superior results compared to others. The 3 nuclei samples also resulted in PCR amplifications showing that the designed system is sensitive enough to amplify also from low nuclei numbers. However, using samples numbers higher than 300 resulted in no PCR amplification, indicating that nuclei numbers of 500 or 1.000 interfere with a successful PCR reaction. Together, the results demonstrated that the optimum sample range is between 200-300 nuclei and that the system is sensitive enough to amplify from low nuclei numbers. Thus, for further experiments a number of 200 nuclei per reaction was used.

Fig12. PCR amplification for depicting the sensitivity of the PCR reaction using restriction digestion with *TaqI*. The optima can be observed at 200-300 nuclei, while the samples start to saturate at more than 300 nuclei.

Next, it was asked whether pollen nuclei isolated using fresh water and from stored acetone samples can be used as template for a subsequent PCR. To do so, fresh water and stored acetone samples were used for PCR-based pollen typing. It was found that *TaqI* is not compatible with acetone sorted samples, so it was decided to use a different restriction enzyme, i.e. *XhoI*, with similar function as *TaqI*. It was found that *XhoI* is working efficiently in both systems resulting in consistent PCR amplification even from stored samples (Fig13). Therefore, *XhoI* together with the acetone sorted samples was used for further experiments.

Fig13. Comparison of PCR performance of various pollen isolates (different extraction methods and pretreatment of nuclei prior to PCR amplification). For all approaches 20 PCR replicates were performed. N = Number of successful PCR reactions resulting in PCR amplicons.

4.2.3 Pollen nuclei genotyping based on targeted amplicon NGS analysis

Both acetone and fresh pollen nuclei samples were suitable for efficient PCR amplification (Fig13). However, to decipher whether PCR amplicons from both samples are compatible with NGS and a bioinformatic pipeline, various PCR amplified Col/Ler hybrid pollen samples were sent for NGS and analyzed through a bioinformatic pipeline (Fig15). To do so, pollen nuclei samples from acetone and water samples were split into 40 batches of 200 nuclei each, i.e. 8.000 nuclei in total per sample. Prior PCR all samples were digested with *Xho*1. To monitor PCR efficiency, from each reaction half of the PCR product was quality controlled by gel electrophoresis and the other halves of each positive reaction were pooled and sent for NGS (Genewiz). To exclude locus-specific differences, two independent loci containing gRNA target sequences (14a and RD1) were analyzed.

The different samples were compared based on i) total coverage of amplicons, ii) phread score of NGS in both samples and iii) range of amplicons (mapping quality of amplicons at defined loci). 85 to 90 percent mapped reads were obtained as trimmed reads from NGS raw data, further 21 to 67 percent reads were mapped from the resultant trimmed reads. Most of them were on target region depicting significant results for the mapping and alignment of both acetone and pollen sorted samples (Fig14). Despite sample-specific differences, both acetone-stored and fresh pollen samples resulted in reads of sufficient quantity and quality to decipher HR outcome and frequency at both independent targeted loci. Thus, both samples can be used for further analysis. However, in most cases acetone isolates will be utilized due to its convenience in storage.

Fig14. Quantitative overview of the reads recovered from NGS sequencing of acetone or water isolates. a. NGS results for 14a -Acetone sorted pollen nuclei b. NGS results for 14a -Water sorted pollen nuclei c. NGS results for RD1 -Acetone sorted pollen nuclei d. NGS results for RD1 -water sorted pollen nuclei.

4.2.4 Analysis pipeline of NGS reads to measure HR outcome and frequency at defined loci

NGS was employed to check amplicons from target sequences from pollen nuclei in high-throughput. A bioinformatic pipeline was setup with the ultimate aim to analyze the effect of artificially induced DSBs at target regions in *A. thaliana* Col/Ler hybrid plants using a dCas9-MTOVIB fusion protein from paired end reads (see 4.3). To do so, acquired reads needed to be sorted according parental reads/molecules and recombinant reads (indicative of an HR event at a given locus, either CO or NCO-GC). Next Illumina sequenced raw sequence data was acquired from Genewiz. In Illumina sequencing a linker is ligated at the end of each DNA or RNA molecule called adaptor creating sticky ends during the library preparation. Adaptor trimmed and filtered sequences were used to avoid false assemblies and to exclude low-quality sequences for downstream processing. Adaptor contamination can lead to NGS alignment errors, since they are synthetic and do not occur in the given sequence naturally. It can also increase the number of unaligned reads in the sequence.

Fig15. Flowchart of the bioinformatic pipeline used for processing of raw reads.

After checking the quality of the reads, the reference sequence was generated (Col ecotype). Bowtie 2, a fast and memory efficient tool for aligning sequencing reads on to long reference sequences, from the IPK Galaxy server was used for alignment of paired end reads. Its outputs are in SAM (Sequence Alignment Maps) format, which enables its interoperability with a large number of other tools including GATK and SAMtools. In the pipeline SAM output by Bowtie 2 was used to create sorted BAM (Binary Alignment Maps). They are compressed binary

equivalents of the SAM files and comparatively more efficient for working within the software interface.

SNPsplit was the next tool used in the pipeline. It is an allele specific alignment sorter designed to read the alignment file in SAM/BAM format which further determines the allelic origin of reads that covers already known SNP/InDel positions (polymorphisms between Col and Ler). The reference genome/sequences marking all known SNP positions which are present in the genotype were provided. SNPsplit also marks the positions of InDels and skipped positions (N). SNPsplit gives the output in two different formats, the first one comprises the SNPsplit report in .txt format in a simple user interface format and the second one is SAM/BAM output which can be viewed in the Integrative genome viewer (IGV) platform. The SNP coverage report represents reads which are either specific to a parental genome or conflicting ones (possible recombinant molecules). It also shows the reads which are unassignable.

Further analysis of BAM files in IGV gives an overall picture of the coverage and shows individual amplicons with probable SNPs in the sequence, enabling to sort out the recombined region in the assembly. IGV is a high-performance visualization tool for interactive exploration of large, integrated genomic datasets. IGV supports a wide variety of data types, like array-based and next-generation sequence data, and genomic annotations.

After visualization, analysis is done using python/CRIS.py. CRIS.py is a simple and highly versatile python-based program which analyses NGS data for various user specified modifications from one or many samples. The pipeline output is used to select recombinant molecules within amplicon sequence assembly.

The tailored bioinformatic pipeline was tested and verified by analyzing NGS sequences generated from previous pollen typing sample. The analysis revealed site specific polymorphisms in the sequences enabling to identify reads originating from Col and Ler pollen nuclei as exemplified for gRNA At2g46510 on chromosome 3 (Fig16). Moreover, putative recombinant molecules, i.e. haplotype switches, could be identified at low frequencies as well.

Fig16. Recombination events caused by gRNA At2g46510 in chromosome 3, the recombined part represents the portion of Col and Ler genomes.

This system will be employed for analyzing pollen nuclei genotyping of transgenic plants generated by *Arabidopsis* transformation for studying induction of site-specific meiotic DSBs (see 4.3).

4.3 Harnessing the endogenous DSB induction complex via CRISPR/Cas9 to induce meiotic DSBs

Selected and activity verified gRNAs from the protoplast assay (see 4.1) were combined together with dCas9-MTOPVIB generating CRISPR/Cas9-based expression systems to harness the endogenous DSB induction complex in order to trigger site-specific meiotic DSBs in *A. thaliana* hybrid plants (Col/Ler).

4.3.1 Setup of a CRISPR/Cas9-based system for targeted meiotic DSB induction

Five constructs were generated consisting of three components: first a catalytically deactivated Cas9 (dCas9) fused in frame via a linker sequence (XTEN) to MTOPVIB, second a gRNA expression module (U6 promoter driven expression of gRNAs; Table 4), and third pHTR5 driven Yellow fluorescent protein (YFP) fused to a nuclear localization signal (NLS) enabling to monitor transgene expression within reproductive plant structures. These components were assembled in pTRANS260d (conferring plant resistance to Glufosinate ammonium upon stable genetic insertion).

Fig17. Generalized representation of construct employed. dCas9- MTOPVIB module is linked through XTEN linker protein joined with gRNA incorporated together with yellow fluorescent Protein with nuclear localizing signals.

A. thaliana Col/Ler F_1 plants and *mtopvib* plants were stably genetically transformed mediated by *A. tumefaciens* with generated dCas9-MTOPVIB constructs targeting various genomic regions (Table 11). *mtopvib* plants were transformed in order to check for complementation of the *mtopvib* phenotype via the transgene, suggesting functionality of employed dCas9-MTOPVIB in the designed constructs. Homozygous *mtopvib* mutants transformed with the dCas9-MTOPVIB transgene showed restoration of fertility, i.e. wild silique length and seed setting, suggesting the dCas9-MTOPVIB functionally complements the *mtopvib* phenotype.

Fig18. Agrobacterium-mediated stable genetic plant transformation. (a) Transformation using floral dipping protocol. (b) Flowering Col/Ler hybrid plants used for transformation. (c) Transformed and bagged Col/Ler hybrid plants to avoid cross-contamination of materials/seeds. (d) Plants with fully matured siliques used for seed collection.

4.3.2 Isolation and selection of transgenic plants

Stable genetically transformed F₂ Col/Ler hybrid plants carrying a transgene insertion were selected based plant resistance against Glufosinate ammonium (PPT) conferred by the transgene. Moreover, *mtopvib* mutant plants were additionally resistant to Sulfadiazine due to a tDNA insertion disrupting *MTOPVIB* function conferring corresponding resistance. To isolate transgenic offspring plants, media containing Glufosinate ammonium and Sulfadiazine was used (Col/Ler - Glufosinate ammonium containing MS media; mutant *mtopvib* - Glufosinate ammonium and Sulfadiazine containing MS media) to screen for transgenic plantlets (Fig19). After selective screening, resistant plantlets were transferred in pots containing soil.

Fig19: Screening for transgenic offspring plants using MS media and plate selection. a. Transgenic plants screened in MS media containing Glufosinate ammonium and Sulfadiazine. b. Positive control, i.e. Col/Ler wildtype without a transgene in normal MS media, c. Negative control, plates containing Glufosinate ammonium and Sulfadiazine for Col/Ler wildtype.

Table12. Plantlets recovered from selective media screening for transgenic lines for each construct/genotype.

Plant (inserted construct)	Number of transgenic plantlets isolated	Selective media used
<i>mtopvib</i> homozygous mutants (dCas9/MTOPVIB/B2303+B000/ pHTR5)	7	MS-PPT+SUL
<i>mtopvib</i> heterozygous mutants (dCas9/MTOPVIB/B2303+B000/ pHTR5)	13	MS-PPT+SUL
F1 hybrids (dCas9/MTOPVIB/B2303+B000/ pHTR5)	18	PPT
F1 hybrids (dCas9/MTOPVIB/B2303+(14a1C+At5g46490)/ pHTR5)	51	PPT
F1 hybrids (dCas9/MTOPVIB/B2303+(At2g46510+RD1)/ pHTR5)	60	PPT

Due to random assortment of homologous chromosomes during each meiotic cycle each heterozygous target locus (Col/Ler) can become homozygous (either Col or Ler) in F₂ plants inhibiting the detection of HR events in this locus. Thus, ecotype-specific InDel markers were selected near the gRNA target sites to enable genotyping of transgenic F₂ plants at a given target locus, either as heterozygous (Col/Ler) or homozygous (Col or Ler). To confirm specificity of selected marker, initially different site-specific primers were designed to check the heterozygosity at the targeted loci in WT Col, Ler or Col/Ler hybrid plants. Genomic DNA of these plants was used for InDel genotyping and PCR resulted in two size-differential amplicons for F₁ hybrids and single amplicons of varying size for Col and Ler ecotypes, respectively, confirming specificity of developed marker (Fig 20). Thus, isolated transgenic plants were genotyped with the markers (Table6) revealing approximate mendelian pattern of segregation (Table 15).

Table13. Genotyping primers designed for InDel markers.

gRNA	Forward Primer/Reverse Primer	Position of InDel	Amplicon Size (Col/Ler)	Size of InDel Marker
14a1C	CGTTAGCATGAGACGCTCCAC/ CTGCTCGTGTGGAAATTACTGGTG	16720760	506/471	35
At2g46510-CH5	GGTTCTGGACAATGGACACCTG/ CATGTTCGTCCTCAACA GCTTTGC	26725072	937/630	37
At5g46490	GTCACAACCATCAAATCCTTGC/ ACCACAACCTCCTCCCA CAG	18852738	401/367	307
At2g46510-CH3	GAGGAAGTGGAA GCTGAAA GAC G/ CCCGCTGTTCCA GTCTATCC	22071935	1129/975	154
RD1	AATGCCGTTGCTGAGGCTAC/ TTTCTCTGACGGTTCGCCTCATC	11297711	343/293	50

Fig20. InDel genotyping of Col, Ler and Col/Ler F₁ hybrid plants at 14a1C showing differentially-sized PCR amplicons. Note, since amplicon sizes were comparatively short, a 2.5% agarose gel was used for gel electrophoresis. The buffer used was 0.5% TBE.

Table14. Segregation of markers near the gRNA target sites based on InDel genotyping within isolated transgenic lines.

Construct	Col	Ler	Hybrid
14a1C	15	19	49
At5g46490	6	14	32
At2g46510-CH3	9	14	33
At2g46510-CH5	12	14	28

In order to estimate the expression level of transgene from the insertion(s) in individual selected transgenic lines, plants were analyzed microscopically for expression of YFP-NLS. Depending on the expression levels plants were classified into three different classes: High expressing transgenic lines, medium expressing transgenic lines and low expressing transgenic lines (Fig 21).

Fig 21. Transgene expression of YFP-NLS (green) in selected transgenic lines. A. Low expression transgene signal. B. Medium expression transgene signal C. High expression transgene signal.

Approximately 25% of plants for each construct showed medium expression levels and around 45% of them showed high expression signals, while the remaining plants showed very low transgene expression levels. YFP-NLS expression level denotes the presence of the constructs delivered during the transformation in transgenic lines. Among high expression plants, those ones that were heterozygous at the target locus, were selected for further studies, i.e. for the analysis of HR frequency and outcome at targeted loci via single pollen nucleus genotyping.

4.4 Future prospects:

Due to lack of time considering also the current circumstances and the impact of COVID-19, it was not possible to dissect HR frequency and outcome at each target site through the developed novel single pollen nucleus genotyping approach (see 4.2). However, pollen samples could be collected from all plant materials and will be used for single pollen nucleus genotyping in order to dissect HR outcome and frequency at target sites. Preliminary experiments were performed to

elucidate HR frequency and outcome at some of the loci (section 4.2), demonstrating that the novel single pollen nuclei genotyping approach together with the developed bioinformatic pipeline can be harnessed for measuring frequency/outcome of site-specific HR based on haploid pollen nuclei in high-throughput.

5. Discussion

CRISPR/Cas9 is employed widely for improving crop production and making plant breeding more efficient due to its unprecedented ability to generate targeted and sequence defined genome edits in plants^{7,11,46,69,70}. It emerged as powerful tool for precise crop improvement via gene knock-in, knockout, replacement, point mutations etc. It was also studied for its potential to manipulate meiotic HR, i.e. targeted meiotic recombination, but the detailed molecular mechanism for controlling site directed CO formation is not unraveled yet. Initial studies in yeasts harnessing genome editing tools to induce site-specific artificial DSBs to trigger CO formation were successfully performed^{71,72}. However, similar approaches are still to be employed in plants. In this work it was explored whether the CRISPR/Cas9 system can be harnessed to induce via recruitment of the endogenous DSB induction complex site specific meiotic DSB formation and trigger HR in *Arabidopsis*. To analyze meiotic HR outcome at distinct targeted loci at high throughput a novel via single pollen genotyping approach was explored and established consisting of NGS of targeted amplicons from pollen nuclei together with a tailored bioinformatic pipeline.

5.1 Targeted meiotic HR

In this work it was explored to induce site-specific meiotic HR harnessing the endogenous DSB induction complex via the CRISPR/Cas9 system, i.e. dCas9-MTOPVIB, which has not yet been successfully performed in plants. Previous studies showed successful targeted somatic HR induction in *Solanum pimpinellifolium*. Somatic induced DSBs resulting in somatic HR events were germinal transmitted assessed based on different fruit colors due to different *PHYTOENE SYNTHASE* (PSY1) alleles implicated in carotenoid accumulation. An HR increase of up to 14 percent compared to wildtype was achieved, suggesting that somatically induced meiotic HR can be used for allele replacement in crops. In addition to targeted somatic DSB approaches also targeted meiotic HR approaches, involving reciprocal exchanges of large chromosome regions at precise sites, possess a great potential for precise crop improvement. Molecular pathways mediating HR in somatic and meiotic cells are mostly similar^{73,74}. However, a major difference is that somatic DSBs spontaneously form while meiotic DSBs are endogenously induced by SPO11 endonuclease during prophase1 in leptotene. SPO11 forms a complex with MTOPVIB to initiate meiotic HR by inducing DSBs. The repair in somatic cells is typically mediated by sister chromatid repair while during meiosis HR is biased towards inter homologous repair favoring CO formation^{75,76}. The formation of CO during meiotic HR offers several benefits and manipulation of crossover frequency and distribution is an attractive method employed in several crops such as *Oryza sativa*, *Pisum sativum* and *Solanum lycopersicum*⁷⁷.

In a nutshell, beneficial variants could be readily identified via targeted HR events triggered by site-specific DSBs through harnessing genome editing tools such as CRISPR/Cas9 to improve existing elite cultivars. Since meiotic HR events are more frequent when compared to somatic HR events due to different repair template choice (inter homologous repair versus inter sister repair) targeted meiotic recombination approaches are likely superior in terms of induced frequencies when compared to somatic HR⁷⁸. Moreover, targeted meiotic recombination events are possibly readily transmitted to the offspring generation.

5.2 Harnessing dCas9 to recruit the endogenous meiotic DSB induction complex to target sites in hybrid plants

The offspring generation derived from an F1 hybrid differs from its parents, while it carries the combination of characters from both parents. A similar scenario also occurs with their genomic composition, the offspring carries the genome from both parents. Hybrids are important for studying combinations of characters in the populations, especially for molecular and genetic studies⁷⁹. On the contrary, in an Inbred population, individuals are similar to each other in their genotype due to continuous inbreeding.

CRISPR/dCas9 is a reengineered version of Cas9 in which the endonuclease activity is inactivated enzymatically. dCas9 enabled for instance targeted expression of genes through recruitment of transcriptional effector domains without causing irreversible DNA damaging mutations⁴⁸. Hence, it allows regulation of endogenous gene activity without modifying the genome in plants^{49,80,81} or non-plant species such as yeast⁸². In this work it was explored to utilize dCas9 instead of an active Cas9 fused to MTOPVIB (part of the endogenous DSB induction complex) to induce site-specific meiotic DSBs by recruitment of the endogenous DSB induction complex through dCas9-MTOPVIB to target sites. In comparison to Cas9, dCas9 is not involved in the cleavage of target sites. It facilitates delivery of the construct, i.e. MTOPVIB in conjunction with SPO11 forms the endogenous DSB induction complex, to catalytically cleave targeted sites during meiosis in order to stimulate meiotic HR. Together, dCas9-MTOPVIB was employed to recruit the endogenous DSB induction to targeted loci.

Similar studies were performed in yeast that demonstrated a 3-fold increase in DSB frequency at target sites, when dCas9-Spo11 was directed to the QQR binding site⁵³. Moreover, the employed Gal4-Spo11 and dCas9-Spo11 (with gRNAUAS1) fusions also induced DSBs at an independent site within the YCR048W coding sequence, containing an additional specific binding sequence. These studies demonstrate the successful application of distinct DNA binding modules including CRISPR/dCas9 to induce meiotic DSB formation at specific binding sites⁵³. Thus, targeting the endogenous DSB induction complex holds great promise to induce also in plants targeted

recombination, and hence dCas9 was used to target MTOPVIB as part of the endogenous DSB machinery to trigger site specific meiotic DSBs.

To do so, initially gRNA candidates targeting loci within polymorphic regions between ecotypes Col-0 and Ler-0 and competence for meiotic HR were selected and tested *in planta* via CRISPR/Cas9 based on protoplast transfection to induce site specific editing analyzed via deep amplicon sequencing. *In silico* analysis revealed the presence of target specific edits confirming *in planta* activity of the majority of selected gRNA sequences. These gRNAs were further combined with dCas9-MTOPVIB and constructs were employed in *Arabidopsis* Col/Ler hybrid plants and in *mtopvib* mutant plants via agrobacterium-mediated stable genetic transformation. In *Arabidopsis*, this system based on dCas9-MTOPVIB is working efficiently, as it fully complements the *mtopvib* mutant phenotype, suggesting formation of an active DSB induction containing dCas9-MTOPVIB. In addition, employed dCas9-MTOPVIB constructs do not interfere with the endogenous DSB induction in hybrids, as in all isolated transgenic lines no fertility defect was observed and thus pollen samples were collected. In addition, genotyping of transgenic lines revealed roughly Mendelian segregation ratios at targeted loci (i.e. either Col or Ler inbreds or hybrids at target sites) further suggesting no negative impact on plant reproduction upon transgene expression (indirectly assessed by co-expression of YFP from the transgene). The outcome of induced DSBs during male meiosis in these plants at target sites will be evaluated using a novel in this study developed NGS amplicon sequencing approach to genotype single pollen nuclei from these plants.

5.3. A novel targeted NGS amplicon sequencing approach to genotype single pollen nuclei in high-throughput

Using the described system above it is possible to analyze meiotic recombination outcome in transgenic plants generated due to polymorphisms (SNPs or InDels) present in both parental genotypes flanking targeted sites. A sudden haplotype flip in a sequence indicates a recombination event in the progeny.

Pollen contains DNA representing the outcome of male meiosis prior to fertilization of the female flower part during reproduction. The process of fertilization generates variation in the upcoming generations due to genetic variation assured by meiotic HR. Here it was successfully attempted to develop a methodology for storing and isolating pollen nuclei isolates from *A. thaliana*. It was established that the pollen can be stored for (at least) one month at -80°C in acetone and can be further used for subsequent pollen nuclei typing. This allows convenient pollen storage prior further downstream analysis removing the temporal barriers in performing pollen related experiments.

Measuring meiotic CO via multi-locus genotyping of single pollen grains in barley was one of the first attempts to efficiently monitor meiotic recombination in individual pollen nuclei and avoids the necessity to generate large segregating populations⁶¹. The pollen was also utilized to investigate recombination at DNA sequence level in barley, by combining flow sorting of haploid pollen nuclei of barley with single cell genome sequencing⁵⁰. This study also revealed that segregation distortion is almost absent if directly measured in the pollen, which makes pollen a suitable resource for measuring meiotic recombination events⁵⁰. In short, pollen nuclei genotyping is capable of revealing the recombination patterns in absence of segregation distortion. However, all methods rely on whole genome amplification (WGA) of every single pollen nucleus due to their limited haploid DNA, thus limiting the number of analyzed samples. Therefore, pollen nuclei were utilized, in order to develop a novel WGA-independent method to study the recombination pattern in *A. thaliana* Col/Ler hybrids at distinct loci in high-throughput.

The acquired data highlighted that a PCR can be successfully performed from isolated pollen nuclei. Three pollen nuclei are sufficient as PCR template while PCR yield and success rate substantially increase with increasing numbers of employed nuclei until saturation is reached (refer section 4.2.2. and Fig12). An optimum range of 200-300 pollen nuclei per PCR was found while the PCR started to saturate with increasing nuclei numbers. To isolate pollen nuclei of high-quality suitable for PCR, different extraction methods using acetone or water were utilized. Pollen nuclei sorting events depicted that water isolated samples on storing at -80°C lead to significantly decreased events however, on the contrary the acetone isolated samples were better upon storage at -80°C. For fresh pollen isolates water extraction performed better than acetone. Acetone being an organic solvent and pollen storage in it a very low temperatures may explain its better performance compared to water, while the water isolated samples could be prone to higher relative humidity which led to desiccation and poor performance in pollen typing. Furthermore, reliability of acetone isolates for providing better high throughput data (Fig14) suggested that the acetone samples can be used conveniently without any experimental barriers. The better performance of stored acetone samples can provide liberty in performing the pollen typing experiments unlinked to flowering time. This methodology can be implemented to other plants too for experimental purposes, where pollen is needed for molecular studies.

In context of a PCR reaction, an intact pollen nucleus is not always accessible for PCR amplification and therefore various treatments were explored to improve nuclei accessibility for a PCR. Initially a proteinase K treatment was performed to digest the outer layer of nuclei (nuclear membrane/envelope) and DNA/nuclear associated proteins showing inconsistent results including no amplification; likely due to the enzymatic nature of proteinase K digesting the DNA polymerase in the reaction mixture despite prior heat inactivation. Even when increasing the heat inactivation incubation time, the proteinase K hindrance was consistently observed. Furthermore,

a combination of sonication together with proteinase K to shear nuclei in addition was opted, but not succeeded. Therefore, trials to utilize proteinase K were stopped. As alternative restriction digestion was performed with *TaqI* and *XhoI* enzymes. Applicability of both enzymes increased PCR yield and success rate likely due to increased template accessibility through the enzymatic DNA fragmentation. However, *XhoI* depicted slightly superior and consistent performance when employed with Phusion buffer in the reaction. The performance of *XhoI* depicted 100% success rate of PCR reaction in both stored acetone and fresh water samples (Fig13). The pollen storage and nuclei isolation method can also likely easily be utilized or adopted in other crops. The method posse's advantages for off-season experiments or when the experiments are not synchronized with the flowering time.

Together, a novel single pollen nuclei genotyping approach was successfully established to analyze meiotic recombination rates/outcome at distinct loci based on NGS analysis without prior WGA. Thus, selection of target loci and their further modification could lead to precise and accurate generation of desired variation in the genome. Furthermore, NGS analysis of the recombination loci *in silico* can give us a clear picture of the editing event occurring in target of interest in the genome. This technology can offer huge advantage to the breeders for manipulating the gene of interest or Flanking region around target.

5.4 Bioinformatic analysis and detection of recombination events via target amplicon sequencing from pollen nuclei:

Several whole genome mapping studies were performed to locate the regions of meiotic recombination and genome wide variations before and after meiosis^{62,83,84}, while targeted next generation amplicon sequencing approaches for detecting recombination events directly in pollen nuclei has yet not been performed in plants without prior WGA due to the limited haploid DNA content of single pollen nuclei. In this work a bioinformatic pipeline was established, that is capable of detecting recombinant molecules within NGS samples from target amplicons of *A. thaliana* hybrid plants in order to decipher HR outcome and frequency at target loci. Thereby, enabling the recognition of possible CO and/or gene conversion events within targeted amplicons/regions.

The *in silico* analysis was carried out through a tailored pipeline based on similar methods to measure meiotic recombination as in yeast^{82,82,85}. Paired end adapter trimmed data from Illumina sequencing was aligned against the mapped reference using Bowtie2 to obtain memory-based alignment. The BAM output of Bowtie2 was processed with the SNPsplit software for allele specific alignment marking differential polymorphism in either of the reference and sorts the reads mapping accordingly, classified as unassigned or conflicting reads. The unassigned and

conflicting reads depict the probable region of possible recombinant molecules. Therefore, in order to access recombined loci, SNPsplit report is mapped in IGV. The map of the mapped amplicons upon visualization shows the recombined loci in either of the parents marked by flanking polymorphisms. Further analysis via python/ CRIS.py depicts the percentage of DSB finally converting into recombined loci in Col and Ler genomes.

It was attempted to integrate the DSB induction mechanism with bioinformatic analysis to get an overview of events in Col and Ler genomes. Flanking SNP and InDels served as markers for identifying recombination events. Thereby making this system a novel method for measuring recombination frequency quantitatively. Similar studies in barley were performed previously using single cell whole genome amplification approaches combined with KASP genotyping. It offers the opportunity to efficiently monitor meiotic recombination in individual pollen nuclei and avoids the necessity to generate segregating populations^{50,61}. Here, it was successfully explored to amplify short specific amplicons containing polymorphism facilitating the detection of recombination events through further *in silico* analysis.

6. Conclusion

Targeted DSB induction leading to site specific edits by employing selected gRNAs using the CRISPR/Cas9 system was successful *in planta*. Active gRNAs were further combined with dCas9-MTOPVIB and resulting constructs were transformed into *Arabidopsis* Col/Ler hybrid and *mtopvib* mutant plants. Employed dCas9-MTOVIB functionally complemented *mtopvib* suggesting formation of an active DSB induction containing dCas9-MTOPVIB. In addition, from all isolated transgenic lines the genotype was established (i.e. either Col or Ler inbreds or hybrids at target sites) and pollen samples were collected in order to evaluate whether targeted meiotic DSB induction and HR can be triggered.

A novel single pollen nuclei genotyping approach was successfully established to analyze meiotic recombination rates/outcome at distinct loci based on NGS analysis without prior WGA. To do so, a bioinformatic pipeline was tailored to analyze NGS based pollen amplicon samples enabling pollen genotyping in high throughput. Due to current circumstances including COVID-19 the final analysis of generated materials was delayed. However, pollen samples from transgenic lines were already collected for further analysis via the NGS based single pollen genotyping pipeline, which will be analyzed soon to evaluate whether targeted meiotic DSB induction and HR can be triggered.

This system could also likely be adopted or adjusted for the use in other plant species, since the meiotic DSB induction complex is conserved across species, CRISPR/Cas9 can be employed in other plant species and pollen samples can be easily isolated from various plants⁸⁶.

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